

BRIDGE-BS

Blue Growth Incubators | Service Dynamics | Empowered Citizens

D8.1 INTEGRATED POLICY REVIEW AND DIALOGUE IN THE BLACK SEA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000240

DELIVERABLE NAME	
ID: 8.1	INTEGRATED POLICY REVIEW AND DIALOGUE IN THE BLACK SEA
RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	ICBSS
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TYPE	Report
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU
FILE	BRIDGE-BS_D8.1
REVISION	V2
DUE DATE	31.05.2023
SUBMISSION DATE	20.07.2023
CALL	H2020-BG-2018-2020 (Blue Growth)
TOPIC	BG-11-2020

DOCUMENT HISTORY			
REVISION NO	REVISION DATE	MODIFICATION	AUTHOR
V0	21.06.2023	Document Creation	Georgia Chantzi (ICBSS), Elpida Besi (ICBSS), Maria Perez (CETMAR), Rosa Fernandez (CETMAR)
V1	30.06.2023	First Version	METU IMS
V2	13.07.2023	Second Version	ICBSS, CETMAR

CLASSIFICATION	
This document is:	
Draft	
Final	X
Confidential	
Restricted	
Public	X

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000240

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY¹

Blue economy (BE) is fundamental for the economic growth and sustainability of the Black Sea countries. Nature and human driven pressures on the Black Sea marine and coastal ecosystems over the past 50 years however, have made the sea basin extremely vulnerable, impeding any efforts for a sustainable and resilient economic development.

Acknowledging these risks, the Black Sea countries have placed importance on supporting Blue Economy development in a sustainable manner. At **regional level**, all Black Sea countries have endorsed the two most inclusive and representative regional frameworks, the Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea (CMA) and its scientific pillar, the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (Black Sea SRIA); while they participate in regional projects and partnerships, and in bottom-up consultations focusing on blue economy (e.g. national consultations for the SRIA Implementation Plan).

At **national policy level**, not all countries have adopted national strategies and policies targeting all blue economy sectors. However, this is not indicative of their lack of interest in investing in the blue economy sectors' potential, rather than a gap in going forward with knowledge-based policy making that could translate European and international guidelines into national policies.

The **BRIDGE-BS project** was launched in 2021 with the aim to fill in this gap and advance the science-based development of blue economy in the Black Sea, though an inclusive and impact-targeted strategy.

Within this context, the present report provides a **baseline assessment of national policies and strategies** in relation to existing European and international policy frameworks; firstly at sector-level, focusing on established and emerging Blue Economy sectors; and secondly, cross-sectoral, focusing on three overarching priorities, i.e. multistressors impact on Black Sea ecosystems, innovation and entrepreneurship, and capacity building and skills.

For the purposes of the present assessment, desk research and consultations with different groups of policy stakeholders were implemented during the period June 2021 - March 2023. The report identified policy gaps, challenges and opportunities **for further action at policy and operational levels**, to be addressed by both the BRIDGE- BS project and all involved stakeholders.

The report will serve as a basis for further science-policy dialogue and knowledge activities tailor-made for policy stakeholders. It will also support the ongoing research and services development under the BRIDGE-BS project, in a targeted and result-oriented manner based on actual needs and priorities.

Overall, good examples of cooperation and performance have been identified. It is observed also, that some blue economy sectors are more developed than others. **Established BE sectors** i.e. coastal and maritime tourism, shipbuilding, fisheries and maritime transport, show higher development, mainly due to existing infrastructure, countries' long experience, and high profit that feeds further development. Most prominent **emerging sectors** with strong potential that require further support in order to boost their activity are marine renewable energy and aquaculture. Challenges in these sectors are related to lack of, or outdated infrastructure and facilities, access to technology and

¹ The deliverable is slightly revised to reflect the comments of the reviewers received during the project monitoring (as of 7 July 2023) concerning the dialogue activities outputs and next steps.

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funding. The least developed sector, but with increasing interest among the scientific communities, is blue biotechnologies, due to lack of legal framework, funding, awareness about the sector, scientific knowledge and skilled workforce.

Aside from any sectoral gaps, bottlenecks are observed cross-sectoral, such as lack of skills to meet current needs; access to funding; data sharing; coordination of stakeholders; and mitigation of environmental stressors. These are amplified further by other regional and international stressors, like the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine and the Asian market infiltration in the region, and other regional and national socioeconomic stressors like brain drain, lack of investments and unemployment.

An overview of policies and BE sectors is included in Table 1 below. A sectoral overview per country is attached as ANNEX I.

In parallel, continuous coordination among all involved stakeholders at both national and transnational levels remains the number one priority and prerequisite for successful efforts to address common barriers for sustainable development. In this context, three overarching nodes **i.e. multistressors impact on ecosystems, innovation and entrepreneurship, capacity building and skills**, which are in line with the overall BRIDGE-BS concept and nodes (Service Dynamics, Blue Growth Incubators, and Empowered Citizens), were used as discussion catalysts with national and regional stakeholders to further the science-policy dialogue for a sustainable blue economy in the Black Sea.

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	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Priority by regional framework	CMA, SRIA, EU Black Sea Synergy, Black Sea Commission	CMA, SRIA, EU Black Sea Synergy, Black Sea Commission, UN SDG 14	CMA, SRIA, EU Black Sea Synergy	CMA, EU Black Sea Synergy, Black Sea Commission	SRIA	CMA, SRIA, EU Black Sea Synergy	CMA, SRIA, EU Black Sea Synergy
Priority at EU level	EU Green Deal and new approach for the Sustainable Blue Economy, MSFD	CFP and the fisheries policy package adopted on 21 February 2023, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, MSFD, MSPD	CFP and the fisheries policy package adopted on 21 February 2023, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, MSFD, MSPD	EU Green Deal, the Smart and Sustainable Mobility Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action Plan	EU Green Deal, the Smart and Sustainable Mobility Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action Plan	EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future, EU Biodiversity Strategy; MSPD	EU Algae Initiative
Priority at national level	BG, GE, RO, TR	BG, GE, RO, TR, UA	BG	BG, GE, MD, RO,	BG, RO, TR, UA	BG, GE, MD, RO, TR, UA	increasing interest but no activity
Existing national policy frameworks	RO, TR	GE, TR, UA	TR	BG, MD, RO		BG, GE, RO, TR, UA	
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - underwater cultural heritage - small-scale boating - untapped 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - job generator - wetlands-breeding grounds - available fishing fleets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - offshore solutions - sturgeon and mussels cultivation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - connectivity potential within and beyond the Black Sea basin - ports' capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - availability of shipyards - high-quality infrastructure - long experience - job 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - wave and offshore wind energy - hydropower - solar energy - marine mineral resources mining - decarbonisation strategies being 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - enhance knowledge transfer from research to market - promote blue skills & social awareness

	niche markets			- short-sea shipping	generator	adopted in Europe and at global level	- create more jobs in the sector
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - seasonality - infrastructure - branding - skilled workforce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - overfishing - dated equipment (e.g. vessels) - skilled workforce - low prices for fishermen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of suitable locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - connection with inland - digitalisation - deep-sea shipping - connection to other BS ports - weak ferry services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asian market integration - business decrease due to privatisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - oil and gas limited exploration - high costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of legal frameworks facilitating development of sector and high-value novel products - high research costs
Good practices at national/regional level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Tempus Project - Kaliakra site (Bulgaria) 	BlackSea4Fish Project		Black and Caspian Sea Project			

Table 1. Overview of EU, regional and national policies and BE sectors

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i. Multistressors impact on ecosystems

Stressors in natural systems can be caused by natural processes or by direct influence of human activities and can be –loosely- defined as processes that damage ecosystem health, harm organisms, and hurt the well-being of coastal populations. These stressors can impact all organisms, their populations, communities, landscapes, and seascapes in some way. The Black Sea basin's geographical position makes it vulnerable to a number of human caused stressors that combine to impact the Black Sea; forming “multistressors”. In addition to these multistressors, climate change also impacts the ecosystem.

Consultations have shown that, understanding multistressors and their impact to ecosystems, is a hard task for the majority of stakeholders. The use of “science-language” becomes a barrier that is further enhanced by their not so easily visible and direct consequences, thus making multistressors less endorsed by policy, business and the general public.

At policy level, the Black Sea countries have environmental and marine policies and strategies. At the EU level, the countries are relatively behind; Bulgaria has approved the MSP Directive (MSPD)² recently (May 2023)³; while in Romania is still under development⁴. At regional level, Black Sea Commission countries have marine monitoring activities and voluntarily report data annually. There is also active cooperation between the Black Sea Commission and The Danube Commission.

The main challenges are located in the national regulatory and monitoring frameworks of non-EU member states that are not required to translate existing EU Directives, e.g. the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSP), into national and local policies in order to support knowledge and mitigation of multistressors.

Insufficient top-down coordination between ministries within countries and also between Black Sea countries is an obstacle to an effective implementation of strategies and policies that often exist only on paper. At the same time, there is not sufficient national funding to support the implementation of these policies.

Lastly, an evaluation of the impact of military activity on the Black Sea ecosystem and associated businesses is needed including from munitions, unexploded ordinance, and floating mines. The Russian invasion of Ukraine has significantly slowed down momentum for increasing the readiness of data from the north-eastern Black Sea.

ii. Innovation and entrepreneurship

Established maritime sectors such as transport, shipbuilding, fisheries and coastal-maritime tourism make a substantial contribution to the region's overall gross value added (GVA) and blue economy employability. And yet, emerging sectors such as blue-biotech, and to some extent renewable marine energy, increasingly offer notable opportunities for greater diversification in local value-chains.

The recent external shocks have forced adaptation to fast-changing conditions; priorities are changing fast, giving space to new innovation initiatives to support actual needs. Encompassing resilience to current and future shocks, as well as competitiveness on the global market must be fully developed; sustainability is and will remain the central challenge for these sectors.

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0089>

³ MSP Bulgaria <https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/countries/bulgaria>

⁴ MSP Romania <https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/countries/romania>

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In this sense, national policies need to adapt in order to meet present challenges. In the past years, new initiatives and instruments have been adopted at national and local levels in the Black Sea countries, with the aim to make new ideas available and productive, promote local businesses and support innovation.

Policy stakeholders are more receptive to including support to innovation and entrepreneurship in blue sectors. However, there is still a gap in understanding the blue economy and the scope to make suitable decisions on where to put the efforts.

Local actors are innovation triggers, but bottom-up approaches have proven not fruitful in many cases, requiring support from top-down ones. In this context, the role of intermediating actors and enablers could contribute to merge both and develop a joint interactive process that requires time to make it stable, continuous and effective in delivering results (long-term). Existing clusters are good candidates for creating blue economy relations, acting as moderators between businesses, science and policy makers.

Eventually, policy-making and decision-making bodies should be made more aware of the potential of blue economy for local sustainable growth and jobs: there is a significant amount of available knowledge on the existing problems around the Black Sea, existing research and available solutions. Their members should be encouraged to adopt innovation and promote the blue economy.

iii. Capacity building and skills

For the Black Sea countries, the blue economy sectors provide a broad range of job opportunities, esp. for young people. However, while there has been significant advance in the Black Sea region to achieve a common understanding of what blue economy is; it is noted that there is limited knowledge on what blue skills entail or what the current market demands are.

At the same time, the pandemic outbreak, and the subsequent new trends and technological advance, created a gap in skills for the majority of the existing workforce in the region.

Ocean literacy can help develop public marine policy, promote a more responsible behaviour towards the ocean and encourage young people to start a career in the blue economy or in marine science. Similarly, the concept of Ocean Literacy (OL) does not integrate well in the region, as most are familiar with the term but very few know its actual significance.

Raising awareness about OL and the maritime industry's careers among society, research and education communities can attract youngsters to select future professions in the Blue Economy sectors.

There are important initiatives going on at regional level (Black Sea SRIA Implementation Plan and some ERASMUS+ initiatives, etc.) towards ocean literacy and skills development. At national level, the Black Sea countries have adopted policies and strategies to support education, trainings and life-long learning; however these are often fragmented or lack the Blue Economy focus.

Education efforts are limited to academic institutions, mainly universities, and often focus on transversal or soft skills, while in some countries target only one sector (e.g. transport, tourism). In the same context, traditional skills are given preference over modern skills. But, it is the complementarity of both that provides sustainable and inclusive development of the Blue Economy activities. Furthermore, it proves to be difficult ensuring an inter-university alignment for a joint master or dual supervision programmes due to bureaucracy.

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At the same time, it is important to consider the imbalance between coastal and inland communities in addressing blue skills development. Taking into consideration that waters are interconnected and the Ocean has an impact far beyond the coastal territories, blue skills development should not be excluded from the agendas and activities of inland regions.

There is a common understanding that, in order to invest in blue economy jobs requires a strong workforce by investing in education. Skilled workforce is the backbone of economic development but policy stakeholders are not familiar with blue skills and fail to pinpoint the market-driven and social-driven needs for their support. Evidently, there is need for training policy makers and people in policy-delivery to leverage the region's capacity for proposing and setting up new mechanisms and investments in skills' development and capacity building.

Concluding, it is important to underline that the overarching principle for the successful development of sustainable Blue Economy lies with inclusivity and coordination of all involved stakeholders both in a top-down and a bottom-up approach.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Blue economy is fundamental for the economic growth and sustainability of the Black Sea countries. However, pressures on Black Sea marine and coastal ecosystems over the past 50 years have made the sea basin extremely vulnerable, impeding any efforts for a sustainable and resilient economic development.

Stemming from the need to mitigate stressors' impact and support sustainability in the Black Sea, the **BRIDGE-BS project** was launched in 2021 with the aim to identify a safe operating space within which a sustainable blue economy can flourish. To do so, the project will develop predictive tools and capabilities necessary to understand and predict the impacts of climate and human driven multistressors on the Black Sea ecosystems.

One of BRIDGE-BS overarching objective is to develop an inclusive and impact-targeted strategy in order to ensure and facilitate the uptake of project's results beyond its duration. To this end, BRIDGE-BS ensures the engagement of different groups of stakeholders from the outset of the project, and the development of an informed and well-connected Black Sea community, including all relevant groups of stakeholders, scientists, industry and policy-makers.

In this context, the present paper aims to provide a **baseline of policy gaps, challenges and opportunities for Blue Economy in the Black Sea** in order to, on the one hand, facilitate an interactive dialogue with the relevant policy stakeholders, and on the other hand, support the research conducted under the BRIDGE-BS project for the development of services and tools based on actual needs and priorities.

The report is divided into two complementary parts. In the **first part**, the document provides an assessment of national policies and strategies for established and emerging blue economy sectors, in relation to regional and EU policy frameworks. In the **second part**, the report continues with a cross-sectoral evaluation of blue economy development in the Black Sea, focusing on three overarching priorities, i.e. multistressors' impact on ecosystems, innovation and entrepreneurship, capacity building and skills, as discussed with national and regional stakeholders in the Science – Policy Dialogue Forum for a Sustainable Blue Economy⁵ (Thessaloniki, 29 March 2023).

The assessment identified a number of **fields for further action at policy and operational levels**, to be addressed by both the BRIDGE-BS project and all involved stakeholders i.e. policy-making and policy-delivery entities, funding agencies, business, researchers and academia, and the general public.

At **policy level**, a dedicated BRIDGE-BS Work Package (WP8-Science-based policy making for Blue Growth) will build on this report to develop targeted dialogue and knowledge activities with the aim to address policy-gaps; to support knowledge-based policy advocacy and to co-develop and ultimately propose an action plan for the future (2030 Blue Roadmap for the Black Sea).

1.1. Methodology

Methodologically this report is based on a) a desk assessment of existing national and regional policy frameworks, b) a series of bilateral and multilateral consultations with national and regional stakeholders, with the aim to identify challenges and priorities for further action.

⁵ <https://icbss.org/event/science-policy-dialogue/>

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The **desk research**⁶ assessed the existing national policies and strategies of the Black Sea countries (Republic of Bulgaria, Georgia, Republic of Moldova, Romania, Republic of Türkiye, Ukraine) in relation to key regional frameworks in order to identify their common ground and evaluate the level of implementation of regional frameworks at national level, focusing on established and emerging blue economy sectors⁷.

For the national perspective, the online research was complemented by the information provided in the detailed country fiches⁸ developed under WP6 - Socio-economics and social innovations of BRIDGE-BS.

For the regional perspective, research used the recently-adopted most inclusive regional frameworks i.e. the Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea and the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda; the EU neighbourhood policy EU Black Sea Synergy; the key documents of the Black Sea Commission; and the UN 14th Sustainable Development Goal “Life below water”.

The regional perspective was complemented further with relevant EU policies, such as the Integrated Maritime Policy of the European Union, and other policies and strategies influencing the marine and maritime realm, such as the European Green Deal (entailing the new approach for a Sustainable Blue Economy), Mission Ocean and Waters, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Common Fisheries Policy and the Action Plan Protecting and Restoring Marine Ecosystems for Sustainable and Resilient Fisheries.

Key Resources

National policies:

Regional and countries fiches developed under BRIDGE-BS project

Intermediate report to D6.5 & Outputs of the 1st Round of Living Labs under WP6: Socio-economics and social innovations of BRIDGE-BS project

Regional frameworks:

Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea (CMA) - <https://black-sea-maritime-agenda.ec.europa.eu/about/our-mission>

Black Sea Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) - <http://connect2blacksea.org/the-sria/>

EU Black Sea Synergy - https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/black-sea-synergy_en

Black Sea Commission - <http://www.blacksea-commission.org/>

United Nations, 14th Sustainable Development Goal “Life below water” - <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal14>

European Policies:

Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP) - <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/oceans-and-seas/integrated->

⁶ Conducted in the period June 2021 – January 2022

⁷ i) Coastal and maritime tourism, ii) Fisheries, iii) Aquaculture, iv) Maritime Transport, v) Shipbuilding, repair and deconstruction, vi) Energy, vii) Blue biotechnologies

⁸ “Blue Economy for the Black Sea Base lines”, developed by SML for BRIDGE-BS project

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[maritime-policy_en](#)

European Green Deal and new approach for the Sustainable Blue Economy - https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/ocean/blue-economy/sustainable-blue-economy_en

Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/oceans-and-seas/eu-marine-strategy-framework-directive_en

Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and the fisheries policy package adopted on 21 February 2023 - https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/policy/common-fisheries-policy-cfp_en

EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 - https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

Mission Ocean: Restore our Ocean and Waters - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en

All the relevant and interconnected points of national policies and regional frameworks were identified and divided into four groups, providing a baseline of opportunities, priorities, weaknesses and gaps at policy level, per blue economy sector.

This preliminary policy assessment was further complemented with **consultations with relevant stakeholders** at national and regional level (Table 1). The identification of the relevant regional and national policy stakeholders built on the established cooperation networks of BRIDGE-BS partners with the target group of stakeholders and policy fora, in order to harness synergies and further strengthen them with concrete actions.

The first round of consultations was launched early in the project under the WP8-Science-based policy making for Blue Economy of the BRIDGE – BS project. Consultations took place in the period June 2021 – December 2022, in the form of bilateral and multilateral meetings, as well as through the participation of BRIDGE-BS partners in relevant meetings organised by the said group of stakeholders. The assessment used also the initial results of the 1st Round of Living Labs performed under WP6: Socio-economics and social innovations of the BRIDGE-BS project.

Policy Stakeholders and Fora

National

- National Ministries and Agencies related to Blue Economy Sectors
- Local and Regional Authorities

Regional

- Organisation of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation (BSEC), and its subsidiary organs, i.e. Committee of Senior Officials, thematic BSEC Working Groups - <http://www.bsec-organization.org/>
- BSEC Parliamentary Assembly (PABSEC) - <https://www.pabsec.org/>
- Black Sea Trade and Development Bank (BSTDB) - <https://www.bstdb.org/>
- Black Sea Commission - <http://www.blacksea-commission.org/>

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- European Union External Action Service (EEAS) - <https://www.eeas.europa.eu/en>
- EC DG for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE) - https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/maritime-affairs-and-fisheries_en
- EU Strategy for the Adriatic and Ionian Region (EUSAIR), and its governing bodies, i.e. Governing Board (GB) and the Thematic Steering Groups - <https://www.adriatic-ionian.eu/>
- Seas, Rivers, Islands and Coastal Areas Intergroup (SEARICA) - <https://www.searica.eu/intergroup>
- Black Sea Assistant Mechanism for the Common Maritime Agenda, and its Steering group - <https://black-sea-maritime-agenda.ec.europa.eu/about/bsam>
- H2020 Black Sea CONNECT CSA - <http://connect2blacksea.org/>
- Council of Europe - <https://www.coe.int/en/web/portal>
- Union for the Mediterranean - <https://ufmsecretariat.org/>
- Central European Initiative - <https://www.cei.int/>

Table 2. Identified Relevant National and Regional Policy Stakeholders

This initial policy review and dialogue exercise resulted in a sector-based assessment of national policies that provides an updated perspective on regional and national policy-related needs and priorities per blue economy sector [section 2 of the present report].

The **second round of consultations with stakeholders** was launched in March 2023, with the Science – Policy Dialogue Forum for a Sustainable Blue Economy⁹ held in Thessaloniki (Greece) with the aim to establish an interactive science-policy communication intended to continue beyond the BRIDGE-BS project.

The event brought together fifty national and regional stakeholders from the policy and scientific communities of the Black Sea, to exchange on the identified results of the initial policy review, focusing particularly on three overarching nodes: multistressors impact on the Black Sea ecosystems, innovation and entrepreneurship and, capacity building and skills.

Participants were divided into three rotating groups of moderated interactive discussions and were provided with a concept note and discussion points prior to the event, for better preparation and facilitation.

The results of this exchange are encompassed in a cross-sectoral assessment of blue economy in the Black Sea [section 3 of the present report].

2. SECTOR-BASED REVIEW OF NATIONAL POLICIES AND REGIONAL FRAMEWORKS FOR BLUE ECONOMY

The Black Sea countries place importance on blue economy as an important driver for sustainable development and economic growth. This is expressed with their participation in regional projects and

⁹ <https://icbss.org/event/science-policy-dialogue/>

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partnerships, and in bottom-up consultations focusing on blue economy (e.g. national consultations for the SRIA Implementation Plan).

At policy level, not all countries have adopted national strategies and policies targeting all blue economy sectors. However, this is not indicative of their interest in investing in the blue economy sectors potential, rather than a gap in going forward with knowledge-based policy making. Besides, all Black Sea countries have endorsed the two most inclusive and representative regional frameworks, the Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea (CMA) and the Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (Black Sea SRIA).

Regarding the pace of progress of the BE sectors, it is observed that some sectors are more developed than others. For instance, marine renewable energy is growing much faster than blue biotechnologies; while the situation in every country is different. For example, in Moldova, maritime transport is the most developed sector, whereas in Türkiye shipping activities are relatively low.

As an overall observation, the sectors that show higher development are coastal and maritime tourism, shipbuilding, fisheries and maritime transport, mainly due to existing infrastructure, countries' long experience, and high profit that feeds further development. Sectors with strong potential that require further support in order to boost their activity are marine renewable energy and aquaculture. Challenges in these sectors are related to lack of or outdated infrastructure and facilities, access to technology and funding. The least developed BE sector is blue biotechnologies due to lack of existing legal framework, funding, awareness about the sector and skilled workforce.

In all sectors, there are good examples of cooperation and performance. Nonetheless, the recent economic crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic and other regional and international stressors, like the war in Ukraine and the Asian market infiltration in the region, have impacted on the BE sectors. At the same time, regional and national socioeconomic stressors like brain drain, lack of investments and unemployment have affected the sustainable development of the sectors.

There is a common understanding that the BE sectors are interconnected. Aside from any sectoral gaps, bottlenecks are observed cross-sectoral such as lack of skills to meet current needs; access to funding; data sharing; coordination of stakeholders; and mitigation of environmental stressors. In this context, cross-sectoral, as well as cross-border cooperation are essential components to any efforts aiming to address common barriers for sustainable development.

2.1. Coastal and Maritime Tourism

Despite the high tourism potential –marine and coastal resources, as well as natural and cultural heritage-, the Black Sea countries are mostly popular for their **urban and seasonal 3S** (sun, sea and sand) tourism. This has impacts on local communities and the environment in multiple ways. On the one hand, part-time, often underpaid jobs result in unemployment and brain drain, mainly in coastal and rural areas; rates of NEETs¹⁰ are high, and it is observed shortage of qualified personnel. On the other hand, overcrowded tourist sites and the unsustainable practices of mass tourism have a severe impact on local ecosystems (i.e. coastal erosion, biodiversity loss, marine pollution/litter, landscape degradation).

Another critical challenge is the **often-outdated facilities or lack of services**, which hampers the efforts of the Black Sea countries to deal with over-tourism and become year-round destinations.

¹⁰ Youth Not in Employment, Education or Training <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/topic/neets>

During the last years, and in the process of sustainable tourism development in the wider Black Sea region, **focus has been placed on tourism diversification**, a strategy aiming to reduce brain drain, increase economic gains and ensure environmental sustainability. Besides, after the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak, **two significant changes have emerged: a)** tourists want to travel in a more sustainable way, reducing their environmental footprint, and **b)** interest in cultural heritage has been increased. This provides an opportunity for local stakeholders to **capitalise on the rich natural and cultural heritage** of the Black Sea and explore niche markets, such as ecotourism and cultural tourism in order to create competitive and resilient tourism offers. In spite of increased interest, coastal and maritime tourism has potential for greater development.

Other types of tourism on which Black Sea countries have put more emphasis during the last years are **MICE tourism**¹¹ (Georgia), **nautical and sport-related tourism** (Romania-Tomis marina, Tourism Strategy of Türkiye 2023), cultural tourism and ecotourism. As for the last, it is observed a link with rural tourism as well as the interconnection of the Black Sea with the Danube River, especially in the cases of Romania (Danube Delta) and Moldova (Danube river cruises is the only coastal and maritime tourism activity of the landlocked country). However, the limited data concerning the abovementioned types of tourism confirm that the need for coordination and data sharing intra-regionally.

In view of the current situation in the region, the **eco-friendly design and construction of tourism facilities** (such as, green buildings) should be a top priority. In **Georgia**, the modernization of infrastructure (mainly, in Tbilisi and Batumi) has contributed to tourism growth. At the same time, **investing in infrastructure** could contribute to the development of niche tourism markets that are currently underdeveloped in the region, such as small-scale cruise tourism, yachting and boating (e.g. higher number of yachts, motor-boats and relevant enterprises, construction of appropriate harbours).

Apart from that, **investment plans in education** (blue skills, tourism studies), in **SMEs**, and **project-based cooperation** between the competent authorities (national, regional, local) are acknowledged as key priorities. A good example of cooperation between universities and industries is the **EU Tempus Project**. Its main goal is the creation of a transnational network of knowledge centres on cruise tourism between the European Union and its eastern neighbours (Georgia and Ukraine).

In the same framework, **pesca-tourism** –local small-scale fishers and tourists have a day trip joining different fishing activities- could play a vital role boosting the environmental consciousness of locals and visitors. In addition, **diving tourism** has a high potential due to the rich **underwater cultural heritage** of the Black Sea (e.g. ancient harbours and wrecks). Therefore, local diving industry can be strengthened with the use of technology (e.g. mapping of submerged archaeological sites, virtual underwater tours) as well as with the development of underwater archaeological museums and diving parks. For example, in **Kaliakra (Bulgaria)**, a number of underwater archaeological sites have been identified to be exploited as a tourism attraction. In this case, it is a major challenge to develop the industry environmentally responsible and with respect to the sites.

2.2. Fisheries

Fisheries are **one of the main sectors** that have traditionally strengthened the Black Sea regional economy. However, during the last decades the sector is facing many challenges emerging from

¹¹ Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions Tourism

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environmental abuse. Unsustainable practices such as **overfishing** and **Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated fishing, discards and incidental catch of vulnerable species**, have contributed to a situation that places most commercial stocks (73%) over biologically sustainable limits¹². These, together with the multiple impacts derived from the climate crisis, threaten both the ecosystem preservation and the associated jobs, particularly in coastal communities. For these reasons, urgent measures have to be taken so as to ensure the successful blue transformation of the sector. The political commitment (2016 Bucharest Declaration and 2018 Sofia Ministerial Declaration) towards the sustainability of fisheries confirms the existence of this urgent need. More recently, the GFCM Strategy for Sustainable Fisheries and Aquaculture in the Mediterranean and Black Sea¹³ adopted in July 2021, entails an ambitious commitment to secure a sustainable future in the region. It aims to preserve the heritage of fisheries and aquaculture as pillars of the livelihoods of the Mediterranean and Black Sea coastal communities, ensuring their transformation into a productive and sustainable food system that contributes to thriving economies and healthy ecosystems. To achieve this, it proposes a set of actions dealing with fisheries management; anthropogenic driven impacts; monitoring, control and surveillance; innovation for a sustainable aquaculture and improving working conditions and social support to these sectors.

The GFCM's flagship project **BlackSea4Fish** constitutes a successful example of the Black Sea's scientific community cooperating to contribute to the sustainable management of Black Sea fisheries, by providing scientific and technical support to the work of the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM)¹⁴ in the region. It underlines the **importance of adopting different control measures** concerning overfishing/IUU fishing¹⁵ and the protection of key fish species (e.g. inspection scheme for turbot fisheries), as well as supporting livelihoods in small-scale fishing communities and promoting decent work. In this context, **exchange of knowledge and expertise** among marine scientists, **data collection and analysis on food systems, contribution to the Data Collection Reference Framework**¹⁶, and the use of **marine technologies** (i.e. IT monitoring tools for fishing vessels, such as underwater drones, fishing sensors and bycatch blocking systems) are key factors for the sustainable development of the sector.

Understanding the need for action, **Georgia, Romania and Ukraine** have adopted policies for tackling IUU fishing, while **Türkiye** has modernized its fishing fleet in order to be more sustainable. **Bulgaria and Romania** (EU Member States) have to comply with EU standards (EU Common Fisheries Policy, MSFD, etc), while **Ukraine** has set "Total Allowable Catch quotas for some rare and valuable species" in the framework of EU trade requirements.

However, the **inspection system of the Black Sea countries should be improved** –through better **legislations**, and allocation of **funding in marine technologies**- in order to conserve and restore fish stocks. In this regard, aligning with EU standards could help to harmonise and coordinate at regional level and pave the way for candidate countries in their adaptation for becoming members. It is worth

¹² FAO. 2022. The State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries 2022. General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc3370en>

¹³ <https://www.fao.org/gfcm/2seas1vision/GFCM2030Strategy>

¹⁴ The General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) is a regional fisheries management organization (RFMO) established in 1949. It has the authority to make binding recommendations for fisheries conservation and management and for aquaculture development by adopting and implementing measures for the management and conservation of Mediterranean and Black Sea marine living resources as well as for aquaculture development.

¹⁵ Illegal, Unreported, Unregulated fishing

¹⁶ <https://www.fao.org/gfcm/data/dcrf/es/>

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noting that action has also to be taken in **Moldova** -even if the country has no fisheries activity- as Moldovan wetlands are important breeding ground regarding the Black Sea coastal fish stock (lower wetlands of the Dniester and Prut are in need of rehabilitation).

Apart from the significant role of innovative and effective monitoring systems, **emphasis should be put on small-scale artisanal fisheries**. Although limited in terms of catches (8.2% of total landings) and economic contribution (15% of revenue), small-scale fisheries represent 84.1% of the vessel units operating in the Black Sea and plays an essential role in generating livelihoods in the region (59% of the total employment, 39% full time equivalent)¹⁷. The creation of appropriate infrastructure (for instance, building docks for small-scale fishing vessels), the access of artisanal fishers to educational and training platforms (blue skills, ocean literacy) and to environmentally friendly fishing technologies, as well as the promotion of their meaningful participation in fisheries cooperatives (limited number) can boost this sector. In parallel, artisanal fishers and entrepreneurs can benefit from diversification, a mechanism to build sustainable business models. In addition to the concept of diversification in coastal and maritime tourism, collecting/recycling nets (ghost nets) and other marine litter (e.g. single-use plastics) through the exploitation of their fishing fleets is an innovative way to reduce marine pollution.

However, it is observed that, even though small-scale fisheries and their diversification have a great potential, they have not been developed widely in the Black Sea (coastal) communities. In order to become game changers, the Black Sea countries should invest in the sector via establishing specialized institutional departments [in contrast to the case of Georgia where the Department of Fisheries (Ministry of Agriculture) has been closed] and, consequently, implementing the above-mentioned Declarations. In this regard, a Regional Action plan for Small-Scale Fisheries in the Mediterranean and Black Sea (RPOA-SSF)¹⁸ was adopted in 2018 as a political commitment by 18 countries, including BG, RO, TK and GE. In 2020, the GFCM has launched the Small-Scale Fishers' Forum initiative (SSF Forum)¹⁹ that is carried out annually to offer support to small-scale fishers and fish workers to further develop their capacities and skills with regard to sustainable small-scale fisheries and livelihoods, as recommended by RPOA-SSF.

2.3. Aquaculture

The political commitment towards the growth of aquaculture in the Black Sea (2016 Bucharest Declaration and 2018 Sofia Ministerial Declaration) confirms its crucial role concerning sustainability in the region. Furthermore, aquaculture is the focus of one of the five targets set up in the GFCM 2030 Strategy for Sustainable Fisheries and Aquaculture in the Mediterranean and Black Sea²⁰. Thus, target 3 *“ensures the sustainable development of aquaculture and its contribution to sustainable food systems in line with the GFCM Strategy for the sustainable development of Mediterranean and Black Sea aquaculture, working towards the resilience of the sector against global challenges such as climate change and pollution”*. For achieving it, the strategy proposes four expected outputs based on governance and responsible investment, promotion of sustainable practices; market perception; and technology and information systems.

¹⁷ FAO. 2022. The State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries 2022. General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc3370en>

¹⁸ <https://www.fao.org/gfcm/rpoa-ssf>

¹⁹ <https://www.fao.org/gfcm/activities/fisheries/small-scale-fisheries/ssfforum/en/>

²⁰ FAO. 2021. GFCM 2030 Strategy for sustainable fisheries and aquaculture in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb7562en>

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Although still scarcely developed in the Black Sea, increased interest in aquaculture is observed, during the last years, as it is considered one of the most promising blue economy sectors. For example, in **Bulgaria** lately, it is observed rapid growth of sturgeon and mussel cultivation²¹; while in **Romania** there are only two aquaculture farms (one mussel offshore farm and one coastal flatfish farm). Apart from the lack of suitable locations (**Bulgaria**) and geographical conditions (**Georgia**), the main challenges are associated with the lack of available data for the sector due to its limited development²², as well as the limited infrastructure and services, such as, high-tech and eco-friendly aquaculture including multi-use platforms, and aquaculture cooperatives in which farmers could actively participate.

In order to bridge these gaps, research (e.g., on seaweed, offshore fish farming, multi-culture cultivation and diving tourism in aquaculture farms), funding (for example, small-scale food producers) and bureaucratic simplification are necessary. In this framework, **Türkiye**, which aims to succeed a high number of aquaculture exports (Vision 2023), focalizes on the potential of clam cultivation and micro-scale clam companies. Overall, many steps must be taken so as the Black Sea countries can benefit from this fast-growing sector.

2.4. Maritime Transport

In general terms, maritime transport is a significant economic sector in most Black Sea countries - except for the low shipping activities of **Türkiye** in the region- via short-sea shipping²³. In **Moldova**, it is the most developed blue economy sector, even though the country is landlocked and has one single port. In **Romania** –where Constanta, the biggest port of the Black Sea, is located- and **Ukraine**, the transport rates of good exports are very high. On the contrary, ferry services (apart from those of Ukraine) and deep-sea shipping²⁴ are underdeveloped. As regards ferries, a typical example is the case of Romania where the construction of the new passenger ferry service has no socioeconomic significance yet.

Although maritime transport is generally well-developed, there are many challenges which are, principally, related to **marine pollution** (plastic litter/microplastics, harmful aquatic invasion from ship ballast water, change of water physical balance, habitat degradation etc.) and the **lack of international cooperation**. With regards to the latter, despite the geographic significance of the Black Sea countries for interconnections, i.e. , a cross-roads connecting Europe – Asia, Black Sea – Central European countries through the Danube (Romania and Moldova), gateway for Armenia, Azerbaijan and the wider Caspian region through Georgia, international partnerships remain low.

As a response to the risks emerged from this situation, priority should be given to **green technologies and digitalization** for sustainable and safe shipping operations, in line with the international conventions, such as the Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments, and the International Maritime Organisation instruments, as well as with the EU Green Deal, the Smart and Sustainable Mobility Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action Plan²⁵. For these reasons, a relevant study (entitled Maritime Single Window) was conducted in Bulgaria. Its results

²¹ “Blue Economy for the Black Sea Base lines”, developed by SML for BRIDGE-BS project

²² ibid

²³ [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Short_sea_shipping_\(SSS\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Short_sea_shipping_(SSS))

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Deep_sea_shipping

²⁵ Maritime safety: at the heart of clean and modern shipping – COM(2023) 268 final
https://transport.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-06/COM_2023_268.pdf

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lead to the need for improving safety of maritime navigation, and establishing e-governance in transport operations, in order to ensure digital and smart connectivity.

In this regard, the following **measures** are crucial: a) B2G (Business-to-government) and B2B (Business-to-business) **electronic data exchange**, b) **green shipping** and **smart port** technology (eco-ports, transforming them into smart hubs, one-stop service), c) use of **liquefied natural gas** (LNG) and **compressed natural gas** (CNG) as an alternative to oil-derived fuels for ships, d) establishment of an **effective port management system**, monitoring illegal litter and oil discharges by ships into the sea, and e) bridging the knowledge gap in the sector, e.g. supporting skills development for the workforce, as well as fostering a closer academia-industry synergy..

Apart from that, the **Black and Caspian Sea Project**, an example of successful cooperation between the European Maritime Safety Agency and the Black and Caspian Seas coastal countries, highlights the need for further **enhancement of the efficiency of maritime administration** in several of the Black Sea coastal countries.

In light of these needed changes, the Black Sea countries try to take steps so as to bridge the gaps. In **Bulgaria**, the port terminals of Varna and Burgas have recently been modernized, the **Romanian National Strategy for a Sustainable Transport** focuses on interconnectivity and inter-modality through a TEN-T axis development²⁶ (using the port of Constanța, the Danube and its canals, railway and road transport systems), while the TRACECA program aims to develop the transport and logistics industry of **Georgia**. In addition to this, the country has received recognition by the European Commission (Certificate of Competency) enabling Georgian seafarers to be employed on ships flying the flag of the European Union countries.

Although these measures have increased the competitiveness of maritime transport in the region, **sustainable and smart connectivity** has not been achieved yet. For instance, the limited connection with the hinterland (Bulgaria, Georgia and Türkiye) should be improved -including navigable inland waterways-, while the port community systems are still weak (Bulgaria). Moreover, in spite of the undergoing efforts to enhance their weak inspection systems, the flags of Georgia and Moldova have not been removed from the blacklist on Paris Memorandum of Understanding on Port State control.

2.5. Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction

In contrast to the very limited activity in **Georgia** and **Moldova**, the other Black Sea countries have a high-quality infrastructure and a long tradition regarding shipbuilding, repair, and deconstruction. In **Romania**, **Türkiye** and **Ukraine**, the rates of ship exports are really high (e.g. 98% in Romania, which also has an excellent higher education system in this sector). In addition, Turkish yacht builders are characterized by a tailor made and high-tech approach; while Ukraine is one of the ten largest shipbuilding countries in Europe. It is worth noting that, before the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, Mykolayiv was Ukraine's main shipbuilding centre, employing about 60% of the city's population).

The challenges that the countries have to overcome are associated with economic and environmental factors; the privatization of a number of shipyards (for instance, in Varna) as a result of the 2008 financial crisis; the fast-growing Asian shipbuilding market; the environmental impact of shipping activities and, consequently, the urgent need for the modernization of the sector.

²⁶ <https://wayback.archive-it.org/12090/20221208011921/https://ec.europa.eu/inea/en/ten-t/ten-t-projects/projects-by-priority-project>

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In this context, a number of priorities for future take-up are identified: a) promoting low-emission, carbon-neutral ships and freight operations in compliance with shipping safety standards, as well as, b) ensuring cheaper and cleaner transport (e.g., from the Black Sea to Central Europe). The Black Sea countries should focalize on green technologies and investments in innovation capacity (research, funding, blue skills). In line with this, Romania has already invested in relevant projects, while in Türkiye the use of LNG propulsion systems and responsible ship recycling practices strengthens environmental protection. Even though the undergoing efforts have to be intensified –in all countries, their background in the shipbuilding industry constitutes an opportunity for the successful blue transformation of the sector.

2.6. Marine Renewable Energy

Energy is one of the most promising sectors in the wider Black Sea region. During the last decades - except for marine mineral resource mining due to limited data and activity-, both oil & gas and renewable energy resources, are high in the national strategies.

With regards to **renewable energy resources**, it is worth noting that the Black Sea is the world largest water body containing hydrogen sulphite; while Türkiye has the highest wave energy potential. Despite of the exploration of alternative renewable energy resources, such as solar energy and biomass, most countries have placed emphasis on researching the potential of wave and wind energy (e.g., feasibility reports on regional scale, data collection/analysis as for energy corridors between different energy sources or the effects of renewable energy on the ecosystem).

Offshore wind energy is currently the only commercial deployment of a marine renewable energy with wide-scale adoption at EU level. Given the significant growth of this sector, the EU Blue Economy Report has included it as an established sector since 2021, while other renewable marine energies are still considered as an emerging sector²⁷. At this point, it is worth mentioning that **Romania** notes the most rapid increase in wind farms in the European Union. With the support of the Connecting Europe Facility²⁸, steps have also been taken to increase interconnection capacity between Romania and Bulgaria and help integrate wind power from the Black Sea coast. In spite of the high potential of offshore wind energy however, its high installation costs constitute a barrier for its development.

For these reasons, and as marine renewable energy is an emerging industry in the region, more research programs should be conducted to adopt the appropriate measures which are associated with: a) financial capacity to introduce new technologies (multi-speed wind turbines, drones to monitor oil installations, etc.), b) blue skills/exchange of know-how with relevant innovation hubs of the European Union, c) the creation of local and regional energy communities to ensure regional cooperation and increased stakeholder participation, d) investments in energy infrastructures

²⁷ European Commission (2023). The EU Blue Economy Report. 2023. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxembourg

²⁸ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/connecting-europe-facility/energy-infrastructure-connecting-europe-facility-0_en

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2.7. Blue Biotechnologies

Blue biotechnologies are the least developed blue economy sector in the wider Black Sea region. Preliminary research studies are noted to be conducted by the scientific communities in the Black Sea countries, however there is no data available yet or any other activity noted.

Despite the lack of knowledge about the possibilities offered by the Black Sea due to its specific characteristics, there are a number of diverse opportunities²⁹ emerging from existing initiatives on blue biotechnologies across sectors in other sea basins.

In order to unleash the full potential of the sector, and taking into consideration that algae are a major source of marine biocomponents, the “Communication from the European Commission: Towards a strong and sustainable EU algae sector” (EU Algae Initiative)³⁰ identifies a set of actions expected to contribute to the development of a robust and sustainable sector. Taking this into account, countries in the Black Sea area should work towards a) improving their legislative systems and adopt measures facilitating the creation of high-value novel products, b) focalize on reducing high research costs, c) close data and technological gaps, d) enhancing knowledge transfer from research to market, e) promoting blue skills and social awareness, and f) increasing the number of jobs in the sector. Therefore, and taking into account the potential benefits emerging from blue biotechnologies (i.e. environmental, social, economic), all relevant stakeholders (policy-makers, industry and academia) should take prompt action.

3. CROSS-SECTORAL REGIONAL ASSESSMENT FOR A SUSTAINABLE BLUE ECONOMY IN THE BLACK SEA

The desk assessment of national policies showed gaps and opportunities for future action for the blue economy sectors in the Black Sea region. At the same time, emphasis should be placed in addressing emerging cross-cutting issues at cross-sectoral level, if the aim is to have an inclusive, sustainable development of blue economy.

Continuous coordination among all involved stakeholders at both national and transnational levels remains the number one priority and prerequisite for successful policy implementation and growth. For policies however to have a tangible impact and be successful, they need to relate with the actual needs of their implementing bodies.

In this context, three overarching nodes i.e. **multistressors impact on ecosystems, innovation and entrepreneurship, capacity building and skills**, were used as discussion catalysts with national and regional stakeholders to further the science-policy dialogue for a sustainable blue economy in the Black Sea. The science – policy consultations were held during the Science – Policy Dialogue Forum (Thessaloniki, 29 March 2023) with the participation of 50 national and regional stakeholders from policy-making and science. The event was developed in three rounds of thematic Working Groups (WGs) of moderated discussions, focusing on i) multistressors on the Black Sea ecosystem, ii) innovation & entrepreneurship, iii) ocean literacy, capacity building & skills, enabling an interactive,

²⁹ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/ocean/blue-economy/blue-bioeconomy-and-blue-biotechnology_en

³⁰ On 15 November 2022, the European Commission adopted the Communication "Towards a strong and sustainable EU algae sector", which identifies 23 actions to unlock the potential of algae and algae-based products in the EU. https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-11/COM-2022-592_en.pdf

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constructive dialogue based on actual needs and priorities. (Discussion point of the working groups are presented under ANNEX 2. More details on the event (press-release, agenda, photos and more are available through the online channels.³¹

3.1. Multistressors impact on the Black Sea Ecosystems

Stressors in natural systems can be caused by natural processes or by direct influence of human activities and can be –loosely- defined as processes that damage ecosystem health, harm organisms, and hurt the well-being of coastal populations. These stressors can impact all organisms, their populations, communities, landscapes, and seascapes in some way.

The Black Sea ecosystem is a unique semi-enclosed basin into which 10 large rivers flow. Its geographical position makes this basin vulnerable to a number of human-caused stressors that combine to impact the Black Sea; forming “multistressors” (see the main Black Sea Multistressors graph). In addition to these multistressors, climate change also impacts the ecosystem.

Although the Black Sea was naturally eutrophic due to permanent nutrient input from its major rivers (Danube, Dnieper, Dniester etc.), until the end of 1960s it was one of the most productive seas with luxuriant pelagic fauna.

However, in the 1970s, the Black Sea underwent a dramatic change, due to the multistressors that caused the degradation of its marine ecosystem. Today, extensive areas of the coast have water quality problems, with high turbidity, high nutrient levels, coupled with frequent occurrence of harmful algae blooms, hypoxia and mass deaths of benthic organisms, etc. The recent Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) reports from the different Black Sea countries show that in some areas the state of the ecosystem is “not good” and actions have to be made to reverse the trend. In addition, most of the fish stocks in the Black Sea are overexploited to the extent that some of them are nearly depleted. Since 1950 the number of economically significant fish species decreased from 30 to 8. These changes limit sustainable blue economy of the Black Sea. The EU 2020 Blue Economy Report highlighted that the Black Sea has the lowest gross value added (2 billion Euros) and number of jobs (140.000) of all the EU sea basins.

The services that Black Sea ecosystems provide to people are closely tied to the fact that multistressors change habitats. The study of this issue in the Black Sea will create knowledge that is applicable all over the world, as species and service dynamics are linked to the availability and quality of habitats that support them (e.g. the availability of good places for fish to spawn, the production of food in upwelling areas, the storage of carbon in areas with high productivity etc.). The support of healthy, well-kept habitats will ensure the resilience of the ecosystems that can produce ecosystem services in a sustainable way.

In this context, the science-policy dialogue focused on the following discussion points:

- Existing national policies, programmes or tools that address multistressors’ impact.
- Identification of other multistressors taken into account by national policies.

³¹ <https://bridgeblacksea.org/index.php/2023/03/31/press-release-for-the-science-policy-dialogue-forum-for-a-sustainable-blue-economy-in-the-black-sea/>

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- Gaps in existing policies and priorities in the policy agenda related to multistressors impact and mitigation.
- Research and innovation community to support policy-making.
- Expected role of BRIDGE-BS in supporting the development of new, or the adaptation of existing policies, in addressing multistressors.

Understanding multistressors and their impact to ecosystems is a hard task for the majority of stakeholders. The use of “science-language” becomes a barrier that is further enhanced by their not so easily visible and direct consequences, thus making them less endorsed by policy, business and the general public.

At **policy level**, the Black Sea countries have environmental and marine policies and strategies. For example, the Bulgarian Ministry of Environment have developed a Maritime Strategy³² and have published several papers related to the ecology and protection of the Black Sea; in Romania and Georgia European Directives such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) have been implemented into national law.

At the EU level, the Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) adopts an environmental approach and aligns with the European biodiversity objectives³³. According to the MSP Directive (MSPD)³⁴, EU Member States were required to have their national plans in place by 31 March 2021. Bulgaria has approved it recently (May 2023)³⁵; while in Romania is still under development³⁶.

Other examples include The Council of Research and Technology in Ukraine which is working on the Blue Economy, projects in Georgia in the field of digital Blue Economy and an accelerator network, and the Blue flag³⁷ label for bathing water as an important marketing tool for tourism very much linked to biodiversity and multistressors.

At **regional level**, Black Sea commission countries have marine monitoring activities and voluntarily report data annually on e.g. pollution, eutrophication, fisheries, biodiversity, climate indicators, port reception facilities, Marine Protected Areas extent. There is also active cooperation between the Black Sea Commission and The Danube Commission.

The main challenges are located in the national regulatory and monitoring frameworks of non-EU member states that are not required to translate existing EU Directives, e.g. the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSP), into national and local policies in order to support knowledge and mitigation of multistressors.

Insufficient top-down coordination between ministries within countries and also between Black Sea countries is an obstacle to an effective implementation of strategies and policies that often exist only on paper. At the same time, there is not sufficient national funding to support the implementation of these policies.

Currently, although some of the stressors are known, no studies exist on ways to deal with multistressors to support policy action. Data gaps exist for most of the multistressors; some countries

³² <https://www.moew.government.bg/en/water/marine-environment/marine-strategy-of-republic-of-bulgaria/>

³³ <https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/>

³⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0089>

³⁵ MSP Bulgaria <https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/countries/bulgaria>

³⁶ MSP Romania <https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/countries/romania>

³⁷ <https://www.blueflag.global/>

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are more advanced than others in terms of monitoring. While stressors such as warming and deoxygenation have better data to base policies on, newly emerging stressors such as ocean acidification and pollution arising from coastal and offshore activities have fewer quality data due to the lack of effective and coordinated monitoring.

Hydropower plants in (Georgian and other) rivers affect river flow into the Black Sea. This blocks fish from migrating upstream and reduces the mean annual water flow to 10% (in Georgia) which increases ocean deoxygenation and causes problems with sediment transport with consequences on coastal erosion. Other stressors identified include urban wastewater, pharmaceuticals, emerging pollutants and nutrients (causing increased eutrophication) from riverine inputs; impacts of coastal erosion on tourism; loss of coastal habitats; underwater noise; and light pollution e.g. from built infrastructure and impacts on fish distribution patterns.

Lastly, an evaluation of the impact of military activity on the Black Sea ecosystem and associated businesses is needed including from munitions, unexploded ordinance, and floating mines. The Russian invasion of Ukraine has significantly slowed down momentum for increasing the readiness of data from the north-eastern Black Sea. Currently in Ukraine, it is not possible to collect new data on the marine environment and activities on the ground and only satellite data are available. There is a need to build partnerships between Ukraine and other countries to ensure Ukraine has access to marine data for the Black Sea.

The key issues that need further discussion and actions proposed to be undertaken in the context of the BRIDGE-BS project are indicated in **Table 3** below.

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Themes for further discussion	Potential fields for action by BRIDGE-BS
Weak integration of EU Directives, e.g. the MSFD and Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSP) into national and local policies. Top-down coordination between ministries and cross-border cooperation is needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase awareness of national policy makers but also of all relevant stakeholders i.e. at the level of the general population, businesses, fishermen, ports, academia, etc, in order to include and keep high in the policy agenda, multistressors and the prioritization of environmental and marine policies. - Harmonize ways to measure eutrophication. - Investigate linear and non-linear connections between cause and effect of multistressors and their impacts and communicate to stakeholders. Non-linear effects can mean that stressors may have different results over time and that is important to communicate.
Bottom-up support and mobilization; training and awareness raising for the general public; people in citizen science.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impact-driven training of local populations on citizen science for monitoring multistressors, with a particular focus on youth.
Policies and tools are needed to support businesses to implement changes that mitigate single and multistressors' impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen the science-policy interface and interaction with industry (e.g. in tourism, fisheries). - Increase knowledge on how to make industry more sustainable i.e. land-sea interactions, how to reduce impacts of multistressors, and sustainable use of resources and waste. - Training of local municipalities to develop monitoring capacity.
Data gaps exist for most of the multistressors; newly emerging stressors have fewer quality data due to the lack of effective and coordinated monitoring. Data access and sharing issues rather than lack of monitoring is	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Future forecasts for the Black Sea are needed e.g. input of river flow data into physical models, and combining with climate change predictions to know whether it will be dryer or wetter in the future. - Collaborate with Black Sea commission to provide data on multistressors to BRIDGE-BS scientists.

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a key hindrance in data.

- There is already data on the impact of hydropower plants on water flow from rivers in Georgia. Forecasting can be done using this data as input to the physical oceanography models of the Black Sea to project what may happen in the future due to these changes in freshwater inflow.
- Filling data gaps e.g. on how stressors caused by tourism (e.g. eutrophication, fishing) impact Black Sea ecology, biodiversity, and bathing water.
- There is a need to distinguish between invasive species that are transported due to shipping vs. entering the Black Sea from the Mediterranean due to warming.
- Efforts to evaluate the impact of the war on the Black Sea ecosystem using available data e.g. Global Fishing Watch and Vessel Monitoring System (VMS).

Table 3. Identified key themes and proposed fields for further discussion and action about multistressors by the BRIDGE-BS project

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3.2. Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Blue Economy

The Black Sea blue economy is largely dependent on established maritime sectors such as transport, shipbuilding, fisheries and coastal-maritime tourism. Together, these sectors make a substantial contribution to the region's overall gross value added (GVA) and blue economy employability. And yet, emerging sectors such as blue-biotech, and to some extent renewable marine energy, increasingly offer notable opportunities for greater diversification in local value-chains. While the recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic, encompassing resilience to this and future shocks, as well as competitiveness on the global market must be fully developed, sustainability is and will remain the central challenge for these sectors.

The potentials offered by the blue economy should be addressed through fully sustainable innovation, both in terms of new business models and technologies, so to minimise and mitigate their impact on local marine and coastal ecosystems.

In this context, the science-policy dialogue focused on the following discussion points:

- Existing national policies, services and tools supporting start-ups, Public-Private Partnerships, networking and clusters in the target sectors.
- Gaps in existing policies and priorities in the policy agenda for the support of innovation and business development.

There is a common understanding among stakeholders that the recent external shocks (e.g. pandemic, war, earthquake in Türkiye, etc) have forced adaptation to fast-changing conditions. Priorities are changing fast, giving space to new innovation initiatives to support actual needs.

In this sense, national policies need to adapt in order to meet present challenges. In the past years, new initiatives and instruments have been adopted at national and local levels in the Black Sea countries, with the aim to make new ideas available and productive, promote local businesses and support innovation. For example, policy strategies for innovation; funding programmes for start-ups; incubators and accelerators; hackathons, demo-days and support structures such as clusters and tech parks. However, these initiatives often lack the blue economy focus.

Policy stakeholders are more receptive to including support to innovation and entrepreneurship in blue sectors. However, there is still a gap in understanding the blue economy and the scope to make suitable decisions on where to put the efforts.

Parliaments, as policy-making and decision-making bodies, should be made more aware of the potential of blue economy for local sustainable growth and jobs: there is a significant amount of available knowledge on the existing problems around the Black Sea, existing research and available solutions. Their members should be encouraged to adopt innovation and promote the blue economy.

Fostering blue innovation and entrepreneurship in the policy agendas with the aim to translate this into targeted policies, means acknowledging some structural needs:

- Support disruption and transformative innovation means accepting failure and attract seed investment.
- Increase involvement of young people:
 - Need better understanding of the potential of the blue economy;

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- Main concepts of innovation should be included in education programmes;
 - Young researchers should be encouraged to initiate businesses from the knowledge they generate.
- Science diplomacy happening at local level to show innovation potential – need to be shared with businesses and investors.
 - Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) have great potential for cooperation – Blue economy should be more visible.

Different levels of intervention in Black Sea countries: some at NUTS 2 level (Bulgaria, Romania, Turkey) but others at national level (Georgia). In Ukraine the blue economy is part of S3. S3 in other sea basins have incorporated the blue economy within their strategic priorities – this can be an inspiration for adopting similar approaches in the Black Sea.

- Crowdfunding for mobilising local funds at small scale:
 - Some successful initiatives for cultural purposes – explore the potential for blue innovation;
 - Requires trust and visibility to be attractive.

Traditional sectors offer a good potential for innovation. In some cases (transport), incentives from the public sector may be required, while in others (aquaculture) there is still a broad scope for development.

Local actors are innovation triggers, but bottom-up approaches have proven not fruitful in many cases, requiring support from top-down ones. In this context, the role of intermediating actors could contribute to merge both and develop a joint interactive process that requires time to make it stable, continuous and effective in delivering results (long-term).

Existing clusters are good candidates for creating blue economy relations, acting as moderators between businesses, science and policy makers. These could move forward with promoting match-making between innovators, raise awareness about actual needs and promote available support instruments.

The key issues that need further discussion and actions proposed to be undertaken in the context of the BRIDGE-BS project are indicated in **Table 4** below.

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Themes for further discussions	Potential fields for action by BRIDGE-BS
Reaching out to national strategies, instruments and funding initiatives at national and local level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of existing (national) programmes and funding operating in the Black Sea countries and assess the potential in supporting a Blue Economy in each country and in the region. - Provide a brief survey to assess the conditions for supporting the Blue Economy as part of their targets (also, cooperation with the CMA national hubs). - Some of them could provide further support to the initiatives promoted by the BRIDGE-BS accelerator and contribute to the project legacy.
Networking with innovation and development agencies in the Black Sea region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen networking and synergies at regional level amongst the development and innovation agencies, funds, clusters from the different countries. - Involving the various local development and innovation agencies and funds as part of the Accelerator panel and the High-Tech Summit.
Bridging the gap between innovators and support instruments (funding, investment, accelerators, etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote a targeted match-making between solution providers (technological operators, start-ups, SMEs) and financing actors operating in the Black Sea (look at synergies with the CMA - goal 3). - Make a link to the foreseen CMA regional events and possible synergies with the Blue Invest in the Black Sea, as discussed under WP7, including the next High-Tech Summit.
Enabling Parliaments and local level authorities as entry point to influence policies through local level science diplomacy	Explore the possibility to raise scientific concerns and solutions into local policy making by getting in touch with local authorities in relevant cities around the Black Sea, as well as parliamentary commissions related to blue economy.

Table 4. Identified key themes and proposed fields for further discussion and action about entrepreneurship and innovation by the BRIDGE-BS project

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3.3. Ocean Literacy, Capacity Building and Skills

Ocean literacy (OL) is defined as *“the understanding of our individual and collective impact on the Ocean and its impact on our lives and wellbeing”*. It is not only about understanding ocean knowledge but also how to govern marine ecosystems sustainably.

Ocean literacy can help develop public marine policy, promote a more responsible behaviour towards the ocean and encourage young people to start a career in the blue economy or in marine science. For the Black Sea countries, the blue economy sectors provide a broad range of job opportunities, esp. for young people. Additionally, raising awareness about OL and the maritime industry’s careers among society, research and education communities can attract youngsters to select future professions in the Blue Economy sectors.

In this context, the science-policy dialogue focused on the following discussion points:

- Existing national policies, programmes or tools that address ocean literacy and skills development.
- Gaps in existing policies and priorities in the policy agenda related to skills development and ocean literacy.
- Identification of suitable interlocutors for “injecting” the concept of ocean literacy to schools and society.
- Development of training programmes for policy stakeholders.

There has been significant advance in the Black Sea region to achieve a common understanding of what blue economy and blue growth are; however it is noted that there is limited knowledge on what blue skills entail or what the current market demands are. Similarly, the concept of Ocean Literacy does not integrate well in the region, as most are familiar with the term but very few know its actual significance.

At the same time, the pandemic outbreak, and the subsequent new trends and technological advance, created a gap in skills for the majority of the existing workforce in the region.

There are important initiatives going on at regional level (Black Sea SRIA Implementation Plan and some ERASMUS+ initiatives, etc.) towards ocean literacy and skills development. At national level, the Black Sea countries have adopted policies and strategies to support education, trainings and life-long learning; however these are often fragmented or lack the Blue Economy focus.

Education efforts are limited to academic institutions, mainly universities, and often focus on transversal or soft skills, while in some countries target only one sector (e.g. transport, tourism). In the same context, the debate addressed traditional vs. modern skills. The latter is given preference over the former, but is the complementarity of both that provides sustainable and inclusive development of the Blue Economy activities. Furthermore, it proves to be difficult ensuring an inter-university alignment for a joint master or dual supervision programmes due to bureaucracy.

At the same time, it is important to consider the differences between coastal and inland realities. Coastal regions (at least some of) have blue skills development in their agendas and activities, contrary to inland regions that are often excluded from any efforts regarding blue economy support. This imbalance needs to be tackled, taking into consideration that waters are interconnected and the Ocean has an impact far beyond the coastal territories.

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There is a common understanding that, in order to invest in blue economy jobs requires a strong workforce by investing in education. Financial support and endorsement of education programmes, PhDs and MSc, in subjects related to blue economy careers is needed. Gender gaps should also be addressed, as well as support to senior workforce.

Additionally, mobility gives the opportunity to increase employee engagement, build a skilled workforce, and generate a more positive and inclusive culture. Mobility actions through study visits abroad on scientific and educational topics related to the blue economy can provide scientists with new techniques, tools and skills, important assets for surviving in the continuously changing working environments and in accordance with market demands and the highest international educational standards.

Skilled workforce is the backbone of economic development but policy stakeholders are not familiar with blue skills and fail to pinpoint the market-driven and social-driven needs for their support. Evidently, there is need for training policy makers and people in policy-delivery to leverage the region's capacity for proposing and setting up new mechanisms and investments in skills' development and capacity building.

The key issues that need further discussion and actions proposed to be undertaken in the context of the BRIDGE-BS project are indicated in **Table 5** below.

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Themes for further discussions	Potential fields for action by BRIDGE-BS
<p>Possibilities to further spread out knowledge and data (esp. in the policy sector) and raise awareness about the importance of the Blue Economy for policy makers (incl. parliament members), tackling also implications for Blue Skills and increasing the understanding of the Blue Skills needs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explore potential for a Black Sea Pact for Blue Skills. - Explore potential for a common (funding) pot in the Black Sea by national funders for blue mobility or for other BE initiatives, such as blue start-ups, etc.). - Explore potential to connect the Black Sea Blue Economy Observatory (under WP6) with other BE observatories at the EU level, S3 platforms, etc. - Learn from experience of BE capacity building (e.g. Aegean University) on transversal/soft skills and connect with the Blue Economy Accelerator (under WP7) - Explore the opportunities to incorporate Blue Economy awareness in BSEC initiative on training young diplomats and connect students with the network of Young Ambassadors (under WP9).
<p>Possibilities to connect initiatives around Ocean Literacy in the Black Sea (bottom-up initiatives) with top-down support by the countries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explore possibilities to engage with University stakeholders, such as the Conference of Vice Rectors of the Danube region. - Engage OL practitioners to promote a community of practice in the Black Sea; study the OL level in the region and also to discuss how to tackle the OL translation in the different countries.
<p>Orient policy trainings (under WP8) to address common understanding of BE concepts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explore possibility to use project outcomes, such as the VBCC for a flexible delivery. - Promote BRIDGE-BS policy documents through targeted trainings (under WP8). - Increase science-policy interpreters.

Table 5. Identified key themes and proposed fields for further discussion and action on Ocean Literacy, Skills and Capacity Building by the BRIDGE-BS project

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4. CONCLUSIONS

For the purposes of the present paper, desk research and consultations with key national and regional stakeholders were implemented, with the aim to assess the current state-of-play of national policies in relation to regional and European policies and strategies, and to identify actual needs and bottlenecks for the successful development of a sustainable blue economy in the Black Sea.

The main conclusions that emerged from this two-year exercise could be summarised as follows:

- Blue economy constitutes a key driver for economic growth in the Black Sea countries which acknowledge the need to support constructively its development.
- Nature and human driven pressures on the Black Sea marine and coastal ecosystems have made the sea-basin extremely vulnerable, impeding the sustainable development of BE.
- Other international stressors, like the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine and the Asian market infiltration in the region; as well as, other socioeconomic stressors, like brain drain, lack of investments and unemployment have affected the sustainable development of BE.
- Regional efforts to mitigate stressors and support BE have been more advanced, compared to national ones, that are fragmented and often miss to address real needs.
- There is still weak integration of European and international directives into national policies.
- There is still a gap in policy and decision making processes to understand blue economy and the scope to make suitable decisions on where to put the efforts.
- Blue economy sectors have progressed over the years - some more than others while the situation in every country is different- but there is still significant potential that remains untapped.
- Established BE sectors: coastal and maritime tourism, shipbuilding, fisheries and maritime transport.
- Emerging sectors with strong potential are marine renewable energy and aquaculture.
- The least developed sector, but with increasing interest among the scientific communities, is blue biotechnologies.
- Overarching priorities, such as mitigation of stressors impact, boosting innovation, access to funding, skills development, are crucial components for any successful efforts.
- There are available tools, services, facilitators and good practices in the Black Sea, that could support the boost of BE sectors and tackle the challenges.

The BRIDGE-BS project was launched in 2021 to enable a coordinated response for the sustainable development of Blue Economy in the Black Sea, through impact-targeted research, dialogue and capacity building activities. In this context, the present paper will feed the ongoing work under BRIDGE-BS, both at policy and operational level. At **operational level**, BRIDGE-BS tools and services development will facilitate the implementation of European and international directives, adapted to respond to Black Sea actual needs. At **policy level**, a continuous exchange with the targeted policy stakeholders will be further supported by tailor-made knowledge and training activities. These will aim to ensure the uptake of project's results beyond its duration, and to support science-based policy making to meet European and international standards. Inclusivity of, and coordination among all involved stakeholders will remain an overarching principle.

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5. ANNEX I. BLUE ECONOMY OVERVIEW PER COUNTRY

BULGARIA							
	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Policy Framework				Strategy for the Development of Transportation System of the Republic of Bulgaria to 2020: connectivity		National Mining Industry Development Strategy to 2030	
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diversification of sector - Small-scale boating - Underwater archaeological heritage (Kaliakra) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job generator - Existence of NGOs facilitates establishment of Producers' Organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sturgeon and mussel cultivation - Offshore solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short-sea shipping - Pan-European Transport Corridors (Varna and Burgas) <p>Modernization:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ferries 2) Maritime Single Window: digitalization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ship repair & maintenance experience - 5 shipyards (Varna and Burgas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil and Gas: Galata and Kaliakra, main drilling points - Galata: Gas storage facility - Wave and offshore wind energy - Marine mineral resource mining: research 	-

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Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seasonality- Sun, Sea and Sand tourism - Yachts/motor-boats: limited - Cruise tourism: underdeveloped - Vulnerable coastal zone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish stocks: poor management - Industrial sector - No fish inspection system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - limited suitable locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deep-sea shipping - Connection with the hinterland - Local actors: no regional autonomy - No Port Community System 	Decline due to: a) Privatization b) 2008 financial crisis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil and Gas prices: low resilience - Marine renewable energy prices: no competitive - Marine mineral resource mining: No activity 	No activity
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GEORGIA							
	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Policy Framework		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Agreement to Promote Compliance with International Conservation and Management Measures by Fishing Vessels on the High Seas (signed) ii. Kiev Protocol on Strategic Environmental Assessment of the Espoo Convention (signed, not ratified) 				Ministry of Transport: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Competitiveness ii. Seafarer education and certification system iii. flag state performance 	

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Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tbilisi and Batumi - Kobuleti and Anaklia: Free Tourism Zones - Modernization of infrastructure - Diving tourism/ MICE tourism - Kolkheti National Park: boating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fishing ports (Poti, Batumi) - Electronic monitoring system for Illegal, Unregulated and Unreported (IUU) fishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased interest - New technologies - Poti: aquaculture farms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TRACECA program: investments - LOGMOS II master plan: source of information - Certificates of Competency by the EU - Gateway for other countries 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 major Oil and Gas pipelines - Hydropower - Marine mineral resource mining: research 	Research
Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seasonality- 3S tourism - Small-scale boating tourism: limited - Ecotourism/ Cultural tourism: no activity - Protected wetlands - Tourist safety: power boats and water scooters - Blue skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overfishing - Fishing trawlers - Department of Fisheries of the Ministry of Agriculture: closed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of suitable geographical conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blacklist on Paris MOU on Port State control - Ferries - Connection with the hinterland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of data - Limited activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil & Gas: limited exploration - Marine renewable energy: Cost-effectiveness 	No activity

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REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA							
	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Policy Framework				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Transport and Logistics Strategy: Deep-sea and short-sea shipping ii. One single port and iii. Connections to other Black Sea ports 			
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Danube: cruise tourism - Yachting and boating: potential 	Wetlands: breeding ground → Black sea coastal fish stock		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation with the neighbouring countries - Inspection system: undergoing efforts 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wind energy potential - Marine mineral resource mining: research 	Research
Gaps		Wetlands: need for rehabilitation	Only inland activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blacklist on Paris MOU on Port State control - Ferries 	Limited activity		No activity

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ROMANIA							
	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Policy Framework	Romanian National Tourism Development Master Plan 2007-2026			National Strategy for a Sustainable Transport: TEN-T axis → interconnectivity and inter-modality		Romania Energy Strategy 2007-2020	
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nautical and sport-related tourism: Tomis marina - Yachting/ Boating: Mangalia's port and St Gheorghe - Cruise tourism: Constanța port - Ecotourism: Danube Delta - Diversification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jobs generator - Uncontrolled, Unregulated & Unreported Small Scale Fisheries: new programs 	Increased added value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Constanta port: the biggest in the Black Sea - Connectivity: Central Europe - Ferries: new passenger - Deep-sea shipping - Short-sea shipping - Midia port - Ploiesti 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-quality infrastructure - Ship exports: 98% - Excellent higher education system - Green technologies and innovation capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subsea natural gas hydrates - Wind farms increase: the most rapid in the EU - Limestone mining 	

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Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seasonality - Coastal erosion - Yachting/ Boating enterprises: small number 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specialized fishing ports - Fishing vessels: low number - Privatization - Market demand - Environmental degradation - Fish migration routes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jobs: decrease - Aquaculture farms: low number 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ferries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asian market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil and Gas: decline - Offshore wind energy: higher costs - Marine mineral resource mining: limited - Environmental monitoring 	No activity
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TÜRKIYE							
	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Policy Framework	Tourism Strategy of Turkey 2023: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation between public and private sectors - Coastal tourism - Ferries - Nautical tourism - Yachting and boating 	i. Vision 2023: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fisheries production - employment in less developed coastal and inland rural regions ii. State Planning Organization: sustainability	Vision 2023: Exports			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Energy and Mining Policy (2017): - renewable energy for electricity generation - diversification of the pipelines - National Renewable Energy Action Plan (2015-2023) 	

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Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature and cultural tourism: growing sectors - Yachting and boating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) production large capacity b) trained work-force 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fishing fleet: the majority of fish production in the Black Sea - Modernization 	Increased interest	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High employment capacity - Long tradition - Exports - Yacht builders: high-tech approach - LNG propulsion systems/ ship recycling practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil and Gas exploration: increased - Wave and solar energy - Hydrogen production: research - Sand mining 	Research
Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation between policy makers and academia - No registered marinas - Cruise tourism - Branding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unsustainable prices for the producers - 1380 coded Fisheries Law: failure to update 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited activity - Connection with the hinterland 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrogen production: higher costs - Marine mineral resource mining: limited activity 	No activity

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UKRAINE							
	Coastal and Maritime Tourism	Fisheries	Aquaculture	Maritime Transport	Shipbuilding, Repair and Deconstruction	Marine Renewable Energy	Blue Biotechnologies
Policy Framework		New strategy: sustainability				Energy Strategy of Ukraine to 2030 (no information is available on marine renewable energy)	
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yachting/ Boating: Odessa marina - Cruise tourism: Odessa and Kherson 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Artisanal and industrial sectors - EU trade requirements - Total Allowable Catch quotas for some rare and valuable species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased interest - Rehabilitation of limans: potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Export of goods - Ferries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the 10 largest shipbuilding countries in Europe - Good quality - Competitive prices - Wide range of vessels - Odessa: 5 ship repair yards - Mykolayiv: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) main shipbuilding centre b) employment capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offshore wind projects - Hydrogen production - Working Group on Hydrogen Energy Development (Ministry of Energy) 	-

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Gaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Cooperation between actors and investors- Spatial planning- Infrastructure- Visa restrictions- Small-scale boating tourism: limited- Know-how	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Fishing vessels: decrease- TAC: vessels and crew → decreased				<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Oil and Gas exploration: limited- Renewable energy: only inland- Marine mineral resource mining: no activity	No activity
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6. ANNEX 2. CONCEPT OF THE SCIENCE – POLICY DIALOGUE FORUM FOR A SUSTAINABLE BLUE ECONOMY (THESSALONIKI, 29 MARCH 2023)

Advance **marine research and innovation in the Black Sea** to identify the operating space for the safe development of human activities under multistressors conditions and to support the development a **fully sustainable Blue Economy** in the sea basin.

Blue Economy Sectors

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MULTISTRESSORS IMPACT ON THE BLACK SEA ECOSYSTEM

STRESSORS in natural systems, caused by natural processes or by direct influence of human activities, can damage ecosystem health, harm organisms and hurt the well-being of coastal populations.

Their effect combines to impact the Black Sea forming **MULTISTRESSORS** that cause degradation of its marine ecosystem.

BRIDGE-BS is creating new, integrated, adaptive, comprehensive models and data analyses to assess the risks posed by these **multistressors** and find out how they affect the functioning and resilience of marine ecosystems.

DISCUSSION POINTS

- Existing national policies, programmes or tools that address multistressors' impact.
- Identification of other multistressors taken into account by national policies.
- Gaps in existing policies and priorities in the policy agenda related to multistressors impact and mitigation.
- Research and innovation community to support policy-making.
- Expected role of BRIDGE-BS in supporting the development of new, or the adaptation of existing policies, in addressing multistressors.

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INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

BRIDGE-BS ACCELERATION PROGRAMME

WHAT – support services to speed up the market uptake of innovative solutions, including through the generation of new waves of dedicated start-ups and SMEs;

WHOM – targeted to Black Sea-based applicants | also open to non-regional applicants interested in expanding their solutions;

WHY – to translate science into business opportunities.

TARGET SECTORS & SUPPORT SERVICES

- ✓ Observation and monitoring
- ✓ Ports, Transport & Logistics
- ✓ Fisheries & Aquaculture
- ✓ Tourism & recreational activities
- ✓ Blue-biotech and related products
- ✓ Sustainable and renewable energy
- ✓ Nature-based services/solutions (coastal/marine)

DISCUSSION POINTS

- Existing national policies, services and tools supporting start-ups, Public-Private Partnerships, networking and clusters in the target sectors.
- Gaps in existing policies and priorities in the policy agenda for the support of innovation and business development.
- Identification of innovative and science-based business models to be promoted through the BRIDGE-BS accelerator.
- Criteria to prioritise specific sectors and support services, according to national/local needs and priorities.

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OCEAN LITERACY, CAPACITY BUILDING & SKILLS

OCEAN LITERACY

- An understanding of our individual and collective impact on the Ocean and its impact on our lives and wellbeing
- Hands on Marine Sciences activities for school children and university students
- Awareness-raising campaigns for citizens
- Build a network to support the ocean literacy community of the Black Sea

INVESTING IN TRAINING & EDUCATION

- PhD Programme on Blue Economy
- Science-Technology-Policy MSc on Blue Economy (in English)
- 2 Summer Schools on Blue Economy sectors

MOBILITY AND EMPLOYMENT

- Virtual Blue Career Centre
- Blue Move activity

DISCUSSION POINTS

- Existing national policies, programmes or tools that address ocean literacy and skills development.
- Gaps in existing policies and priorities in the policy agenda related to skills development and ocean literacy.
- Identification of suitable interlocutors for “injecting” the concept of ocean literacy to schools and society.
- Development of training programmes for policy stakeholders.

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